

EFFECT OF FLEXIBILITY INTERPHASE ON MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF CFRP

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1 Introduction

Interface is board between fiber and matrix resin. Then the concept is known that interface was considered as “interphase” is 3D region having thickness and it has own mechanical property. Therefore, improvements of mechanical properties of composites were succeeded by giving interphase different property from matrix resin [1, 2]. It is considered that mechanical properties of a composite were able to be controlled by active designing interphase.

In this study, it was object that discussing what the “flexible interphase” affects to mechanical properties and fracture behavior. Flexible resin was same type as matrix resin and more flexible than matrix resin was used as interphase of carbon fiber reinforced woven composites (CFRP).

2 Fabrication of Specimen with Flexible Interphase

In this study, reinforcement fiber was carbon fiber, reinforcements were woven fabric, matrix resin was epoxy resin (CEL2021P; DAICEL CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES, LTD.) and hardener was acid anhydride hardener (B0231; DAICEL CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES, LTD.). In addition, epoxy resin which is more flexible than matrix one was used to create flexible interphase. The flexible interphase was created by soaking the cloth in the solution diluted with the acetone for ten seconds (flexible resin : acetone = X : 100 (Treatment concentration is able to be changed by becoming X. For example, If X is 1, treatment concentration is 1wt%.) and drying at 80 degrees for 1 hour. Relationship between weight increasing rate and treated concentration was shown in Fig.1. Weight increasing rate was calculated by difference of cloth weight in before and after treatment. After treatment, resin was impregnated by hand lay-up, and it was

cured (at 110 degrees for 2 hour and 170 degree for 2 hour) by using compression molding press (7MPa)

Fig.1 Relationship between increasing rate of cloth weight and treated concentration.

3 Test Methods

3.1 Static Tensile Test

Specimens were 2ply woven composites for non treated, 1wt%, 2wt% and 5wt%. And warp yarn of woven became longitudinal direction. It was cut width was 20mm, length was 200mm, thickness was about 0.4mm. Test speed was 1mm/min and span length was 100mm.

3.2 Observing Edge Face by Replica Method

Under tensile force load, in-situ observation was done to observe onset and progress of micro fractures by replica method. Specimens were non treated and 2wt%, and 6ply woven to observe easy. Observing started at 30% of max load, after that at including 10%.

3.2 Micro-droplet Test

Micro-droplet test was performed to evaluated interfacial adhesion and interfacial shear strength of flexible interphase, a small droplet of resin was applied to a single fiber. Micro-droplet test machine HM410 (Tohei Sangyo Co.,Ltd) was used with a

fiber pull-out speed of 0.03 mm/min. The maximum load measured before matrix detachment from the fiber is related to the fiber/matrix shear strength. The interfacial shear strength τ was calculated by equation 1,

$$\tau = \frac{F}{\pi dl} \quad (1)$$

where F was the maximum load, d was the fiber diameter, and l was the embedded fiber length.

3.3 Compression test

Specimens were non treated and 2wt%, and 12ply woven. And warp yarn of woven became longitudinal direction. They were cut into 6.5 mm-wide and 134 mm-length, and thickness was about 2mm. Test speed was 1mm/min and span length was 8mm.

3.3 Drop Weight Impact Test

Specimens were non treated and 2wt%, and 12ply woven (thickness was about 2mm) were cut a square, 100mm on a side. A specimen was fixed by plate having 76mm hole in diameter and load was applied by hemispherical indenter with 12.7mm in radius. Applied energy was 40J.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Tensile Test

Relationship between strength and treatment concentration was shown in Fig.2. From Fig.2, when treatment concentration increased, tensile strength was max load around 1wt% and then, it was decreased with increasing treatment concentration. The improvement of static strength and modulus by flexible treatment was confirmed.

Fig.2 Relationship between strength and treatment concentration.

4.2 Behavior of Micro Fractures

The result of observing by replica method was shown in Fig.3. These pictures were typical observing results (80% of max load) and the pattern diagrams showed progress of micro fractures (60, 70, and 80%). Each initial fracture was transverse crack in 90 fiber bundles. Then, in case of non treated specimens, after transverse crack went to end of fiber bundle, the crack progressed to delaminations around 90 fiber bundles. However, the transverse crack of flexible treated one did not progress to a delamination, and the number of transverse cracks in 90 fiber bundles was increased. In each tensile load, length of transverse cracks in 90 fiber bundles, length of delaminations around 90 fiber bundles and the number of filament fracture in a 0 fiber bundle were shown in Fig.4, 5 and 6. In case of non treated specimens, the number of delamination and fiber fracture increased with generation of transverse cracks. On the other hand, in case of flexible treated one, only transverse cracks progressed by breaking composites and little delamination and fiber fracture were increased. It is considered adhesive or fracture toughness of interface around fiber bundles was improved and rapid progressive of cracks was inhibited by flexible treatment.

Fig.3 Onset and progress of micro fractures.

Fig.4 Relationship between length of transverse cracks in 90 fiber bundles and load.

Fig.5 Relationship between length of delaminations around 90 fiber bundles and load.

Fig.6 Relationship between the number of filament fracture in a 0 fiber bundle and load.

4.3 Difference in Fractures between Treatment Concentration

Relationship between the number of transverse crack in 90 fiber bundles and treatment concentration and relationship between delaminations around 90 fiber bundles and treatment concentration were shown in

Fig.7. When treatment concentration increased, the number of transverse crack increased and became max at 2wt% and then, it decreased with increasing in treatment concentration. And length of delamination was decreased and minimum at 2wt% and then, it increased with increasing in treatment concentration. Compared with non treated, in case of 2wt%, a delamination was inhibited and a transverse crack was increased. On the other hand, in case of 5wt%, flexible interphase was thickened and a delamination was increased. So it was considered that strength of 5wt% became low in result of tensile test.

Fig.7 Relationship between the number of transverse crack in 90 fiber bundles or length delamination and each treatment concentration.

4.4 Interfacial shear strength

Fig.8 shows relationship between interfacial shear strength and treatment concentration. Interfacial shear strength was improved by flexible treatment. When the treatment concentration was increased more than 1wt%, the interfacial shear strength became low. Samples of SEM pictures after test were shown Fig.9. In case of non treated, little resin adhered around a filament. On the other hand, much resin adhered around a filament treated by 1wt%. However, when the treatment concentration was increased more than 1wt%, adhered resin became little. It was considered that when the concentration was too high, flexible interphase was thickened, and property of flexible resin appears on a preferential basis and interface fracture transitioned to interphase fracture.

Fig.8 Relationship between interfacial shear strength and treatment concentration.

Fig.10 Relationship between load and deflection in compression test.

Table 1 Result of compression test

Flexible treatment	Strength (Mpa)
Non treated	601
2wt%	659
Increasing rate (%)	
	9.75

Fig.9 Fractures of micro-droplet observed by SEM

Fig.11 Photographs of specimens after compression test.

4.5 Results of Compression test

Relationship between load and deflection was shown in Fig.10, and result of compression test was shown in Table1. From Fig.10, flexible treated specimen showed high load and long deflection. Next, from Table 1, strength of flexible treated was higher than non treated one. Then, cross-section pictures of specimens after compression test are shown in Fig.11. From picture, in case of non treated, there were a lot of delaminations and filament fractures, on the other hand, there were a lot of transverse cracks in flexible treated specimen. It was also considered that the interface property was improved by making flexible interphase.

4.6 Drop Weight Impact Test

Relationship between load and deflection in impact test was shown in Fig.11. Table 2 showed several energy calculated by Fig.11. Energy to max load was absorption energy in the lead up to max load. Energy after max load was absorption energy from max load to breaking composites. From Table 2, max load, energy to max load and energy after max load of flexible treated specimens were higher than non treated one. Next, breaking section photos after impact test specimens was shown in Fig.12. In case of non treated specimen, all fiber layers were fractured at circle in the photo, however in case of flexible treated one, fibers were not fractured, there were bending deformation and many delaminations. The reason why energy to max load was increased was dependent on strength of composites. And, the reason why energy after max load was increased was considered that in case of non treated specimens, brittle fracture progressed, and flexible treated one, ductile fracture progressed.

Fig.11 Relationship between load and deflection in impact test.

Table 2 Result of impact test

Flexible treatment	Energy to max load (J)	Energy after max load (J)	Total Energy (J)
Non treated	4.51	8.01	12.5
2wt%	5.40	8.28	13.7
Increasing rate	19.7 %	3.43 %	9.45 %

Fig.12 Photographs of specimen after impact test.

5 Conclusion

In this study, CFRP with flexibility interphase were made by using flexible resin is more flexible than matrix resin and the influences that flexible interphase exerts static and dynamic mechanical properties of composites were evaluated. The improvements of both static and dynamic strengths were confirmed. From in-situ observation by replica method, the inhibition of progressing brittle fracture was observed and availability of interphase created by flexible resin standing between fibers and matrix was confirmed. It was considered that fracture toughness of interphase around fiber bundles was improved with appropriate concentration of flexible treatment.

References

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